

EARTH SCIENCES

PROBABILISTIC SEISMIC HAZARD ASSESSMENT (PSHA) FOR CONSTRUCTION SITE IN TASHKENT, UZBEKISTAN

Jumaev D.

*Master student at the University of Bristol – Bristol, United Kingdom
PhD at the “Institute of Geology and Geophysics” – Tashkent, Uzbekistan*

Rakhmatov A.

PhD at the “Institute of Seismology” – Tashkent, Uzbekistan

ABSTRACT

The article focuses on evaluating the seismic risk associated with the Yunusobod district, a part of Tashkent, using a probabilistic approach. The study emphasizes the importance of seismic hazard assessments for the safety of infrastructure, particularly in urban areas with dense populations and significant construction demands.

The PSHA methodology employed in the study relies on the total probability theorem, which accounts for uncertainties in earthquake magnitude, location, and ground motion intensity. This approach necessitates comprehensive data collection, including historical earthquake records, seismic source models, and ground motion prediction equations (GMPEs). The study meticulously prepared an earthquake catalog by merging data from various sources and applying techniques like declustering to ensure the accuracy and independence of the seismic events considered.

Seven seismic zones near Yunusobod were selected based on their seismic activity and proximity to the study area. The study calculated the seismic hazard curve for Peak Ground Acceleration (PGA) and derived the Uniform Hazard Spectrum (UHS) for different return periods, which helps in understanding the expected ground motion levels for buildings with varying natural vibration periods. Additionally, deaggregation analysis was conducted to identify the specific magnitude and distance ranges of earthquakes that significantly contribute to the seismic hazard at the site. The results indicate that the maximum design spectral acceleration for Yunusobod is 0.87g for a building with a natural vibration period of 0.15s, which is notably higher than previous estimates for the broader Tashkent area [2]. This finding underscores the critical importance of site-specific seismic hazard assessments, as they reveal variations in seismic risk that may not be captured in broader regional studies.

This article presents a Probabilistic Seismic Hazard Assessment (PSHA) for the Yunusobod district in Tashkent, Uzbekistan. Recognizing the region's high seismicity due to the convergence of the Indian and Eurasian tectonic plates, the study aims to quantify the seismic risk for this rapidly developing urban area. Extensive data collection was undertaken, including the compilation and homogenization and declustering of an earthquake catalog and the selection of relevant seismic zones. The seismic hazard was quantified through the calculation of Peak Ground Acceleration (PGA) and Uniform Hazard Spectra (UHS) for various return periods. All the calculations have been performed in Matlab utilizing number of functions and therefore the procedure much easier to understand compared to other fully programmed methods (e.g., Open Quake, OpenSHA). One of the main aim of this project is to explain the procedure of PSHA in detail, especially for students and beginners.

Keywords: Probabilistic Seismic Hazard Assessment (PSHA), Tashkent, Uzbekistan, Seismic risk, Peak Ground Acceleration (PGA), Uniform Hazard Spectrum (UHS), Site-specific seismic hazard

1. INTRODUCTION

The tectonic regime of the Uzbekistan is determined by the convergence of the Indian and Eurasian plates (Fig. 1). This intra-continental collision region is highly seismic and capable of generating large crustal earthquakes, as evident by the historical seismicity. Many cities such as Tashkent (the capital, population 2,6 million), Samarkand, Bukhara and others have experienced seismic intensity of VIII and IX (MSK). The earthquakes on the territory of Uzbekistan are the most

frequent and dangerous. It was only 1976-1986 years that more than ten violent and destructive earthquakes with $M = 5.5-7.3$ took place. At the beginning of 2024 the population of Uzbekistan is nearly 37 million people. Ensuring the safety and providing earthquake resistance infrastructure for these people is crucial not only for the engineers who making the plan of the structure but also for the researchers who are providing the likelihood of the hazard for this region.

Figure 1. The Topographic map of the Uzbekistan and tectonic condition

The site of interest (Yunusobod), which is considered as a part of the capital city is also located in high seismic zones. Despite having risk of experiencing the strong ground motion, the growth of the population in the urban cities like this makes the demand for complex constructions such as high-rises and residential buildings. Complex constructions need to be safe enough and must match with the seismic codes that based on the seismic hazard values of the construction site. The aim of this research, it to evaluate the seismic hazard of the Yunusobod city through the classical probabilistic hazard analysis method [3]. The critical and complex formula, which combines uncertainties in earthquake size, location and ground motion intensity, is known as the total probability theorem, which is given below.

$$\lambda(IM > x) = \sum_{i=1}^{n_{sources}} \lambda(M_i > m_{min}) \int_{m_{min}}^{m_{max}} \int_0^{R_{max}} P(IM > x | m, r) * f_{M_i}(m) * f_{R_i}(r) * dr dm$$

Where, $\lambda(IM > x)$ –The rate of the exceedance for the intensity measure, larger than x ;

$\lambda(M_i > m_{min})$ –Rate of the earthquake with the magnitude, larger than m_{min} ;

$P(IM > x | m, r)$ –Probability of the having intensity measure larger than x , from an earthquake scenario with magnitude m and radius r ;

$f_{M_i}(m)$ –Probability of expecting an earthquake with magnitude m ;

$f_{R_i}(r)$ – Probability of expecting an earthquake with radius r

2. BASIC DATA COLLECTION AND ADJUSTING FOR CALCULATIONS

Calculation of the seismic hazard for any locations requires sufficient data, including:

- the catalog of the past earthquake in surrounding areas
- the source model characteristic with the boundaries
- recorded ground motion intensities to identify the attenuation law for seismic waves or GMPEs

Making these abovementioned data files ready to process requires much effort. In the next section, the preparation of the much comprehensive catalog and the stages, are going to be discussed in details.

2.1 Making catalog ready for calculations

Since a number of organizations and institutions (USGS, ISC, GEM, SMRM) have collected the information regarding the earthquakes that are happened before and each database contains the records that are not exist in others, it is crucial to combine them together. However, in this procedure some events would be identical, as these sources might be recorded similar events. In this situation these identical events have to be removed from catalog. During this study, because of combining the catalogs from different sources and removing the identical events with Matlab function (*Re-cleaner*), 78423 total events have been collected in excel file.

Magnitude homogenization: As there are many magnitude types that have been recorded so far, including moment magnitude (M_w), surface wave magnitude (M_lh), body wave magnitude (m_b) and energy class (K), these measuring quantities also should be homogenized. In this study all other magnitude types converted into moment magnitude. In order to do this, the formulations from Scordilis (2006) have been used.

Declustering: As the calculations of the hazard values depend on the magnitude and the occurrence rate of the earthquake in selected seismic zones and the distribution of the earthquake follows Poisson's processes, the independence of the events is important. In standard PSHA, the occurrence of earthquakes is modelled using a Poisson process, where the occurrence of a future earthquake is independent of the occurrence of previous earthquakes from the same source (Cornell 1968). In reality, earthquake catalogs are characterized by a

proportion of correlated events that are highly interdependent in space and time. As a result, not-declustered seismic catalogues can provide a biased view of the future spatial variability of seismicity rates, in particular for instrumental catalogues [7]. Declustering algorithms remove events from a sequence, typically using space–time windows that depends on the magnitude of the earthquake (the time window is proportional to the

magnitude of the event) to identify aftershocks and foreshocks. By implementing this method to this study, the dependent events such as foreshock and aftershock are removed from catalog, as a result of which 23955 out of 78423 events have remained as a main-shocks. The results before and after declustering are shown in Figure 2, below.

Figure 2: The comparison of the non-declustered and declustered data in number (a) and in magnitude (b) versus time plot.

By averaging the spatial windowing formulations introduced by Gardner&Knopoff [5], Gruenthal and Uhrhammer (1986), abovementioned-declustering procedures are carried out. As it can be seen from the figure 2(a), there are some sudden jumps in the data number at some points before declustering and after declustering procedure they are smoothed. Declustering

process might not remove all the foreshocks and aftershocks but the level of accuracy is considerable as the number of events decreasing more than three times.

2.2 Earthquake seismic source zones

The source of the earthquakes might be expressed in different way including the area, line or point sources. In PSHA calculations, each point inside the individually extracted source zones are assumed to have same rate of occurrence and equally probable of being

an epicenter for the future earthquake. However in reality, this will not happen in a short period of time and may not happen in a long term.

For simplicity, in this case only the area source zones, which have been prepared as a part of EMCA

project [10] are employed. The total number of zones were 63 and only 7 of them that are close to the study area, have been chosen in this study.

Figure 3: EMCA source zones (a) and the final zones (b) that are important to calculate the PSHA for study site

For simplicity, only area source zones are used. But, it is useful to employ other sources types through the logic tree branching reducing the epistemic uncertainty of the result.

2.3 Ground motion prediction equation (GMPE)

As other fundamental data mentioned above making sophisticated attenuation relationship requires plenty amount of records and time to fit the data and find the relationship between magnitude vs intensity and distance vs intensity. One of those complex recent GMPEs covering not only the fault mechanism but also the soil condition of the study area is the equation for acceleration prediction made by Akkar&Bommer [1] which will be employed in this study later. The overall shape and components of the equation as following.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Log}(PSA) = & b_1 + b_2 * M + b_3 * M^2 + (b_4 + b_5 * M) \\ & * \log \sqrt{R_{jb}^2 + b_6^2} + b_7 S_s + b_8 S_A \\ & + b_9 F_N + b_{10} F_R + \epsilon \sigma \end{aligned}$$

Where, $b_1 \dots b_{10}$ - the coefficients coming from the work of Akkar&Bommer, M - magnitude and R_{jb} - Joyner&Boore epicentral distance, S_s and S_A - soil condition, F_N and F_R - fault mechanism and the $\epsilon \sigma$ - standard deviation

For simplicity, only one GMPE is being used for calculations.

3. CALCULATION PROCEDURES

3.1 Extracting the seismogenic zones and discussion about completeness

Seven distinct seismic zones proximate to the city of Yunusobod have been identified for the purpose of conducting a Probabilistic Seismic Hazard Assessment (PSHA). The rationale behind the selection of these zones lies in the comprehensiveness of the available seismic data within these regions, coupled with the consideration of an optimal distance range of 200-260 kilometers. This distance criterion is paramount, as seismic events occurring beyond this specified range exhibit diminished influence on the site.

Figure 4: Selected zones of the interest and the events distribution within each zones.

Once the final zones, which are considered for the further calculations, have been selected (see Figure 4), the sub catalog comprising the earthquakes in each

zones separately will be made and the completeness of the earthquake sub catalogs within each zones are going to be discussed below.

Figure 5: The completeness comparison through graphical representation for different zones

Table 1

Completeness analysis results for final zones							
Minimum magnitude	Completeness start and end years (duration) of the each zone for different minimum magnitude						
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
4	1960-2010 (50)	1945-2010 (65)	1950-2010 (60)	1950-2010 (60)	1950-2010 (60)	1985-2010 (25)	1950-2010 (60)
4.3	1960-2024 (64)	1930-2024 (94)	1950-2005 (55)	1930-1995 (65)	1940-2024 (84)	1950-2024 (74)	1955-2024 (69)
4.5	1960-2024 (64)	1945-2024 (79)	1950-2024 (74)	1930-2024 (94)	1930-2024 (94)	1930-2024 (94)	1950-2024 (74)
5	1930-2024 (94)	1945-2024 (79)	1920-2024 (104)	1930-2024 (94)	1900-2024 (124)	1930-2024 (94)	1950-2024 (74)

Completeness of the data mostly depend on the minimum magnitude and the data availability of the area. As the sensitive sensors have been deployed since the second half of the 20th century, the earthquakes with

smaller magnitudes had not recorded properly before that time as a result of which the completeness for these magnitudes starting from 1950-1960 years. However, as it can be seen from the Table 1, for larger magnitudes

like 4.5 and 5, completeness period starting earlier. Also, data availability for smaller magnitude have increased dramatically since the beginning of this century as a result of which the seismicity slopes are not matching (see Figure 5) with previous century for magnitudes smaller than 4. Minimum magnitude selection should be based not only on the completeness of the catalog but also from the quality of the infrastructure, earthquake resilience of the study area. Based on both factors, 4,3 has been chosen for minimum magnitude of the events to be considered for calculations.

3.2 The Gutenberg and Richter relationships for final selected seismogenic zones

Figure 6: Gutenberg-Richter relationships for seismogenic zone 1(a) and seismogenic zone 2(b)

Relied on the fitted Gutenberg-Richter relationship and its parameter b, the probability density and cumulative distribution function of the data for given magnitude range (minimum and maximum) have been

calculated, which are plotted in Figure 7. These discretization is important to know the Pdf of the each magnitude, which is the integral part of the total probability theorem.

Figure 7: Pdf of the earthquake magnitude distribution in fitted interval for zone 1 (a), and zone 2 (b)

The level of discretization can and the shag can be changed, in order make the calculation reliable. The more bins acquired, the more will be the level of accuracy.

3.3 Calculation of the seismic hazard curve for the Peak Ground Acceleration (PGA)

Once the discretization of the earthquake magnitude within the each seismic zones have been done (see figure 6), the zones itself will be discretized into pieces

and each piece will be considered equally probable of being the earthquake epicenter. As a result, the distance (R_{ij}) between the earthquake epicenter (each small zones) and the site can be calculated for each discretized mikro-areas. The Pdf of the distances $f_{R_i}(r)$ can be defined as one over the number of mikro-zones within each area source zones (Final zones in this study). Now, only one parameter of the total probability law (see Equation 1) is left and that is the complementary cumulative distribution function (CCDF) of the GMPE results, $P(IM > x|m, r)$. This term is found by the calculation of the intensity measure (see Equation 2) for each earthquake scenario identified by discretization. Once the intensity measure have been calcu-

lated with confidence interval, the cumulative distribution of it will be calculated $CDF(IM < x|m, r)$ and will be subtracted from 1, in order to find the $P(IM > x|m, r)$. Finally, all of the scenarios will be added together as an integral and multiplied by the rate of earthquakes larger than minimum magnitude $\lambda(M_i > m_{min})$ to get the result that is shown in Figure 8(a). As for the soil condition term of the GMPE, based on the soil shear wave velocity of the site ($V_s=600m/s$), B soil class is taken. The predominant type of movement in the faulting for each seismic source is reverse fault [2; 10], though there is a negligible contribution from strike-slip events. For simplicity, the procedure has been carried out considering all of the fault mechanisms as a 'reverse'.

Figure 8: Classical-integration based PGA-hazard curve for the site of interest, represented by mean annual rate (a) and probability of exceedance in 50 years (b)

If the results are compared with previous research outcomes especially the latest hazard curve calculated for Tashkent as a part of Central Asia project by Poggi et al. (2023) and as a part of Uzbekistan by Artikov et al. [2], there is a small differences between them (0.06-0.1g). However, those calculations have been done for Tashkent while this study is specific for Yunusobod city that is a part of the Tashkent and the soil class also is different.

3.4 Uniform Hazard Spectrum (UHS)

The Uniform Hazard Spectrum (UHS) is a visual representation, illustrating the variation in acceleration (velocity, displacement) response of the structures depending on their vibration periods. They are derived from the hazard curves represented in Figure 9(a), in which expected pick accelerations in different return periods are presented.

Figure 9: Hazard curves for different Vibration periods (a) and the Uniform hazard spectrums for different return periods (b)

As it can be seen from the Figure 9, the maximum design (10% probability of exceedance in 50 years) spectral acceleration for site of interest is 0.87g and this value corresponds to the building with a natural vibration period of 0.15s. Acquired result is quite high than the result provided by Poggi et al. [11] whom calculations have shown the maximum acceleration of 0.6g in the buildings that have a natural period of 1s.

3.5 Deaggregation

Deaggregations provide an estimate of the distribution of magnitudes and distances of earthquakes contributing to the hazard at a particular site. It is useful tool to define the magnitude range and location distribution of the earthquakes which have much more effects on the seismic hazard of the site. This fantastic result comes as a result of discretization and computation of the intensities in each bins.

Figure 10. Deaggregation result in (a) 2D and (b) 3D plots when considering all the distances

Figure 10. Deaggregation result in (a) 2D and (b) 3D plots when sitting a limit for distance

Figure 10 clearly shows that the earthquakes with magnitude range of 5.5-6.5 in the distance of 0-60 km have much more contribution on the total hazard in site of interest. This result plays an important role when carrying out the dynamic analysis by applying real earthquake to the structure or the model of it.

4. CONCLUSION

The PSHA conducted for the Yunusobod district reveals that the seismic risk is higher than previously estimated for the broader Tashkent area by Artikov et al. as well as Poggi et al. [2; 11]. The findings highlight the necessity of site-specific seismic hazard assessments, especially in regions undergoing significant urban development. The calculated maximum design spectral acceleration of 0.87g for buildings with a natural vibration period of 0.15 seconds underscores the critical need for infrastructure to be designed in accordance with these updated seismic hazard values to ensure safety and resilience in the event of an earthquake.

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